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MATHEMATICAL CURIOSITY AND MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

Rishell Mae A. Caliosan¹, Cristy Joan C. Cutay², Royen A. Lagat³ & Aldwin T. Miranda⁴

*^{1,2,3,4} Institute of Teacher Education and Information Technology, Southern Philippines
Agri-business and Marine and Aquatic School of Technology (SPAMAST),
Malita, Davao Occidental, Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between mathematical curiosity and the mathematics performance of freshmen pre-service teachers. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing a stratified random sampling technique. A total of 178 students participated in the study. Data were collected using an adopted survey questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe the quantitative variables, while correlation and regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationships among the variables. Results revealed that most freshmen pre-service teachers exhibited a high level of mathematical curiosity, demonstrating a strong interest in mathematics, frequently engaging with challenging material, and enjoying problem-solving activities. The majority of respondents achieved a very satisfactory level of mathematics performance, indicating their development of fundamental knowledge and skills in the subject. Correlation analysis indicated a low but statistically significant relationship between mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance. Furthermore, regression analysis revealed that among the domains of mathematical curiosity, exploration significantly predicted the mathematics performance of the freshmen pre-service teachers.

Keywords: Mathematical Curiosity, mathematics performance, pre-service teachers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is an essential tool in people's lives, enhancing critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Baccay & Jaen, 2016). It plays a significant role in various daily activities, from managing finances to making travel plans and even social interactions. Mathematical concepts can often appear abstract and challenging, making them difficult for students to grasp, which can lead to frustration and disengagement (Sabanal et al., 2024).

The 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results highlight that Filipino students continue to struggle in mathematics compared to their peers in other Asian countries. Their performance remains below the international benchmark, reflecting difficulties in solving mathematical problems and applying strategic methods for problem-solving (OECD, 2023). Similarly, the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) reported that Filipino students performed significantly lower than their global counterparts in both mathematics and science assessments. Furthermore, pre-service mathematics teachers face challenges, such as a lack of deep mathematical knowledge, which negatively affects their ability to teach effectively (Peterson & Cohen, 2019). In response, the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented various initiatives to address curriculum gaps and enhance students' competencies, aiming to improve outcomes in future international assessments.

Despite the commendable performance of some college students in mathematics (Adlawon et al., 2022), many still struggle with the subject (Miranda, 2018) due to low motivation and engagement. These difficulties highlight the need for effective learning strategies, as research suggests that self-regulated learning can significantly enhance mathematics performance by fostering metacognitive skills and discipline (Lumoto et al., 2024). Additionally, students' attitudes toward mathematics remain an

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important factor in their academic success, with positive attitudes promoting greater motivation and persistence in solving mathematical problems (Sabanal et al., 2024).

One key factor influencing student engagement is mathematical curiosity—an important component in deepening mathematical understanding and improving performance. Curiosity drives students to explore mathematical concepts beyond the classroom, leading to better problem-solving skills and conceptual connections. However, research suggests that many students lack mathematical curiosity, which can hinder their ability to engage with complex problems (Rumack & Huinker, 2019). Studies further indicate that students' self-concept and resilience impact their learning process, with resilience serving as a mediating factor between self-concept and mathematics performance (Agtarap & Miranda, 2022). This suggests that fostering both curiosity and resilience may lead to better learning outcomes.

Curiosity can be categorized into four types: exploration (the desire to seek new information), absorption (deep engagement in specific activities), epistemic curiosity (interest in cognitive-stimulating problems), and perceptual curiosity (interest in sensory stimuli) (Doronila, 2012; Baccay & Jaen, 2016). Additionally, problem-solving confidence, approach-avoidance style, and personal control have been identified as predictors of mathematics performance, emphasizing the need for students to develop both curiosity and confidence in tackling mathematical challenges (Villegas et al., 2024).

While several studies have explored factors contributing to mathematics performance, few have examined the direct relationship between mathematical curiosity and academic achievement. For instance, a study found that freshman pre-service teachers with high levels of mathematical curiosity tend to achieve better performance in mathematics (Belicina & Ocampo, 2016). However, there remains a gap in understanding how different dimensions of curiosity specifically impact mathematics performance among pre-service teachers.

Therefore, this research seeks to establish and highlight the relationship between mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance among freshman pre-service teachers in a state college in southern Philippines. Addressing this problem is crucial for enhancing pre-service teachers' overall mathematical curiosity and ensuring their academic success, ultimately contributing to the improvement of mathematics education in the country.

2. OBJECTIVES

The study aimed to determine the level of mathematical curiosity among freshmen pre-service teachers and its relationship with their mathematics performance at a state college in Southern Philippines during the first semester of the school year 2023–2024. Specifically, it sought to:

1. Determine the level of mathematical curiosity according to the following dimensions:
 - 1.1 Epistemic Curiosity;
 - 1.2 Perceptual Curiosity;
 - 1.3 Exploration; and
 - 1.4 Absorption
2. Determine the level of mathematics performance of the respondents.
3. Determine the significant relationship between mathematical curiosity and their Mathematics performance.
4. Determine a regression model of mathematical curiosity that significantly predicts mathematics performance.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational design to explore the level of mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance of freshmen pre-service teachers. Additionally, it aimed to investigate the significant relationship between mathematical curiosity and mathematics

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performance. It also determined the factor of mathematical curiosity that best predicted the mathematics performance of freshmen pre-service teachers.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was an adopted questionnaire from Belecina and Ocampo (2016), known as the Mathematical Curiosity Scale. It consists of four domains with a total of 31 statements, rated on a five-point Likert scale: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The first domain, epistemic curiosity, comprises ten (10) statements; the second domain, perceptual curiosity, contains nine (9) statements; the third domain, exploration, includes six (6) statements; and the fourth domain, absorption, consists of five (5) statements. The instrument demonstrated a high level of reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.94, indicating strong internal consistency.

This questionnaire was deemed appropriate for pre-service teachers, similar to its application in the study by Belecina and Ocampo (2016). Additionally, students' mathematics performance was assessed based on their final grade in the subject Mathematics in the Modern World during the first semester of the School Year 2023-2024.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were freshman pre-service teachers at a state college in Southern Philippines, enrolled during the first semester of the school year 2023-2024. They were proportionally selected from various academic programs, including elementary education, technology and livelihood education, and secondary education with specializations in mathematics, English, and science. The selected students participated in the study by answering an adopted survey questionnaire from Belecina and Ocampo (2016), known as the Mathematical Curiosity Scale. The list of respondents was based on official student records obtained from the school registrar. The distribution of respondents is detailed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

PROGRAMS	POPULATION (N)	SAMPLE SIZE (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	79	44	24.72
2	40	22	12.36
3	83	46	25.84
4	80	44	24.72
5	40	22	12.36
Total:	322	178	100.00

Data Gathering

The data-gathering procedure began with the researchers writing a letter to the Vice President for Academic Affairs (VPAA) and the Dean of the institute to seek permission to conduct the study among freshman pre-service teachers at a state college in Southern Philippines. They also submitted a letter to the registrar's office to request the number of students from the selected respondent pool.

An adopted questionnaire was used as the data-gathering instrument. The researchers distributed the questionnaires to the identified respondents enrolled in the subject Mathematics in the Modern World during the first semester of the school year 2023-2024. These questionnaires were administered directly through classroom visits, ensuring that respondents were given sufficient time to answer at their convenience. Before answering, students were given a general orientation regarding the study's scope and privacy measures. The researchers acknowledged that students' responses could be influenced by concerns about honesty and effectiveness; therefore, participants had the option to remain anonymous. Additionally, the researchers sought consent from the respondents to collect their grades, clarifying that

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participation in the study was voluntary and that they had the freedom to decline or withdraw at any time.

After the respondents completed the questionnaire, the researchers ensured the confidentiality of all collected data. The gathered data were tallied, collated, and tabulated for processing and analysis. Tables were created to illustrate the findings, and the results were summarized and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools with the assistance of statistical software.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Mathematical Curiosity of Freshmen Pre-service Teachers

The research results, as presented in Table 2, reveal the students' level of mathematical curiosity across four key dimensions: epistemic curiosity, perceptual curiosity, exploration, and absorption. The overall mean score of 3.86 indicates a high level of mathematical curiosity, suggesting that freshman pre-service teachers demonstrate a strong interest in mathematics, frequently engage with challenging material, and enjoy problem-solving activities. This finding aligns with the study of Belecina and Ocampo (2016), which similarly concluded that freshman pre-service teachers generally exhibit high levels of mathematical curiosity. They often show a keen interest in learning new concepts, exploring different problem-solving methods, and seeking a deeper understanding of mathematical ideas.

Epistemic Curiosity

In terms of epistemic curiosity, the findings suggest that freshman pre-service teachers are motivated to actively seek knowledge and explore new teaching strategies. This aligns with the observations of Belecina and Ocampo (2016), who noted that freshman pre-service teachers with high epistemic curiosity tend to continue reading about concepts that puzzle them until they fully understand them. Additionally, Sakaki et al. (2024) found that higher levels of epistemic curiosity are associated with increased mind wandering. This suggests that individuals who are more curious tend to let their thoughts drift more often, possibly as they seek new information or experiences. Furthermore, Plubsiri and Chaiyasang (2020) stated that by focusing on building ideas, generating new concepts, providing justifications, and enhancing problem-solving skills, educators can foster a more effective learning environment that prepares students for real-world mathematical challenges.

Perceptual Curiosity

Regarding perceptual curiosity, the results indicate that freshman pre-service teachers actively seek new and stimulating experiences, motivating them to explore the unknown and engage with novel information. This finding aligns with the work of Rumack and Huinker (2019), who observed that freshman pre-service teachers often pursue diverse sensory experiences to broaden their perspectives. Similarly, Chen et al. (2024) found that students with high levels of perceptual curiosity are more likely to explore new environments and embrace different ways of thinking. This tendency fosters deeper cognitive engagement and enriches the overall learning process.

Exploration

The dimension of exploration reflects the eagerness of freshman pre-service teachers to learn about new topics, including historical events, as well as mathematical and scientific concepts. A high level of exploration, as observed in this study, suggests that these students have a strong desire to delve deeper into mathematical ideas, question assumptions, and identify connections between different areas of mathematics. Research has consistently shown that college students typically exhibit a high level of exploratory curiosity (Hartini et al., 2020). This curiosity drives them to explore unfamiliar subjects, discover new perspectives, and approach learning with an open and inquisitive mindset, ultimately enhancing their academic growth and engagement (Schutte & Malouff, 2023).

Absorption

Regarding absorption, the results indicate that freshman pre-service teachers fully engage, concentrate, and immerse themselves in their studies, which enhances learning, promotes active participation, and

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fosters a genuine passion for mathematics. This finding aligns with the work of Rumack and Huinker (2019), who noted that freshman pre-service teachers exhibit a high level of mathematical curiosity related to absorption. Additionally, the study by Adeel et al. (2023) found that students with strong absorption tendencies actively participate in various learning activities that broaden their knowledge and foster intellectual growth. Furthermore, research by Wong and Liem (2022) highlighted that students with a strong inclination toward absorption are more likely to seek diverse learning opportunities, further enriching their academic experience.

Table 2: The Respondents' Level of Mathematical Curiosity.

DIMENSIONS	MEAN	SD	DESCRIPTION
Epistemic Curiosity	3.73	0.42	High
Perceptual Curiosity	3.91	0.45	High
Exploration	3.97	0.47	High
Absorption	3.82	0.48	High
MATHEMATICAL CURIOSITY (OVERALL)	3.86	0.38	High

Level of Mathematics Performance of Pre-service Teachers

The mathematics performance of freshman pre-service teachers is presented in Table 3. A significant number of respondents demonstrated a very satisfactory level of mathematics performance, with 96 students (53.93%), indicating that they have developed fundamental mathematical knowledge and skills. In contrast, the marginal level had the lowest frequency, with only three students (1.69%), suggesting that these students possess minimal mathematical understanding and require additional support and guidance from teachers and peers. The respondents' average mathematics grade is 1.99, with a descriptive level of "very satisfactory" and a standard deviation of 0.276. This suggests that most respondents have a solid grasp of mathematical concepts, although some still struggle to develop proficiency in the subject. Moreover, no student has a grade point average lower than 3.00, which is a positive indicator of their overall performance.

This finding aligns with the research of Dela Rosa and Nacasio (2021), which also reported that college students demonstrated a good level of performance in Mathematics in the Modern World. Additionally, the study by Cabalquinto & Magallanes (2022) found that while most respondents performed satisfactorily, some college students encountered challenges in learning mathematics.

Table 3: The Respondents' Level of Mathematics Performance

RANGE OF SCORES	DESCRIPTION LEVEL	FREQUENCY (f)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1.00-1.49	Superior	7	3.93
1.50-1.99	Very Satisfactory	96	53.93
2.00-2.49	Satisfactory	72	40.45
2.50-3.00	Marginal	3	1.69

n=178; %=100; Mean=1.83; SD=0.276

Relationship Between the Respondents' Problem-Solving Appraisals and Mathematics Performance

Table 4 presents the relationship between mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance among freshman pre-service teachers. The mathematical curiosity dimension "epistemic curiosity" was found to have a low correlation with mathematics performance, as indicated by an r-value of 0.296, but a significant relationship, with a p-value less than .05. This suggests that epistemic curiosity influences mathematics performance among freshman pre-service teachers. This finding aligns with the study conducted by Rahayuningsih et al. (2023), which suggests that students with a greater curiosity for knowledge tend to perform better in mathematics.

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Similarly, the mathematical curiosity dimension “perceptual curiosity” also showed a low correlation with mathematics performance, with an r-value of 0.304, but a significant relationship, as indicated by a p-value of less than .05. While the correlation is weak, it is positive, implying that perceptual curiosity contributes to mathematics performance. This finding is supported by the study of Arthur and Kaku (2024), which highlighted the importance of student interest in this relationship. Their research revealed that positive perceptions of mathematics significantly predict better performance, with interest being a key factor.

The mathematical curiosity dimension “exploration” was also found to have a low correlation with mathematics performance, as indicated by an r-value of 0.327, but a significant relationship, with a p-value of less than .05. Although the association is not particularly strong, it significantly affects freshman pre-service teachers' mathematics performance. Prior research on pre-service teachers found a positive correlation between different types of mathematical curiosity, including exploration, and performance in mathematics (Chen et al., 2024), suggesting that fostering exploration and inquiry can improve mathematical outcomes. Additionally, the study by Hartini et al. (2020) emphasized that curious students are more likely to embrace challenges and engage deeply with mathematical concepts, leading to better results.

Furthermore, the mathematical curiosity dimension “absorption” showed a low correlation with mathematics performance, with an r-value of 0.274, but a significant relationship, as indicated by a p-value of less than .05. While the correlation is weak, it remains positive. This finding is supported by the study of Dela Rosa and Nacasio (2021), which found that various dimensions of mathematical curiosity, particularly absorption curiosity, are positively correlated with mathematics performance. Additionally, Zetriuslita et al. (2021) stated that absorption curiosity has a significant effect on students, particularly those with high levels of this trait. Such students are more likely to engage deeply with mathematical problems, leading to enhanced problem-solving skills and overall performance.

Overall, freshman pre-service teachers' mathematical curiosity exhibited a low correlation with mathematics performance, as reflected by an r-value of 0.361. Nevertheless, the relationship was found to be significant, as indicated by a p-value of less than .05. This suggests that intrinsic interest and fascination with mathematics may influence performance to some extent. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, concluding that there is a significant relationship between freshman pre-service teachers' mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance. This result is consistent with the findings of Wong and Liem (2022), which demonstrated that mathematical curiosity significantly affects performance in mathematics. The findings further suggest that students with higher levels of mathematical curiosity generally achieve better mathematics performance compared to those with lower levels of curiosity. Similarly, Ulum (2022) emphasized the importance of curiosity as a crucial element of learning that can enhance mathematics achievement. Additionally, research by Harackiewicz et al. (2018) demonstrated a strong link between curiosity and math achievement, while Krapp (2019) found that a lack of curiosity contributes to poor performance. However, no prior study has specifically addressed mathematical curiosity and its relationship with the mathematics performance of freshman pre-service teachers, leading to a gap in existing literature.

Table 4. The Relationship Between the Students' Problem-Solving Appraisals and their Mathematics Performance

DIMENSIONS	r-VALUE	DESCRIPTION	p-VALUE
Epistemic Curiosity	0.296	Low Correlation	<0.001
Perceptual Curiosity	0.304	Low Correlation	<0.001
Exploration	0.327	Low Correlation	<0.001
Absorption	0.274	Low Correlation	<0.001
Mathematical Curiosity (overall)	0.361	Low correlation	<0.001

Regression Model of Mathematical Curiosity that Significantly Predicts Mathematics Performance

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Table 5 summarizes the results of the stepwise multiple regression analysis. The results indicate that among the domains of mathematical curiosity considered in this study, only exploration significantly predicts the mathematics performance of freshman pre-service teachers, with a regression coefficient of 0.198 and a p-value of less than .05, implying a significant contribution to the dependent variable. This means that if exploration increases by one standard deviation, mathematics performance will also increase by 0.198.

This result is consistent with the findings of Chen et al. (2024), who stated that exploration curiosity is one of the dimensions of mathematical curiosity that significantly influences mathematics performance. Their study found that students with high levels of exploration curiosity tend to achieve higher performance in mathematics among freshman pre-service teachers. This suggests that encouraging exploration and inquiry can lead to improved academic outcomes in mathematics.

The constant in the model is 3.382, and the regression equation is represented as:

$$y = 3.382 + 0.198x$$

where,

$x = \text{Exploration}$

$y = \text{Mathematics performance}$

Furthermore, the $r^2 = 0.115$, which reveals that 11.50% of the considered data fit the regression model. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a regression model that significantly predicts mathematics performance, with exploration as its predictor. The study by Hartini et al. (2020) emphasized that exploratory behaviors, a component of curiosity, enhance mathematics performance by enabling students to ask questions, test hypotheses, and relate new information to prior knowledge. Understanding how curiosity develops can lead to better educational practices and improved student engagement.

Table 5. Summary of Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients	p-value	Interpretation
(Constant)	3.382	0.000	Significant
Exploration	0.198	0.000	Significant

$$r^2 = 0.115$$

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the findings and statistical results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The results of the study show that freshmen pre-service teachers exhibited a high level of mathematical curiosity. This suggests that they show a strong interest in mathematics, frequently engaging with challenging material and enjoying problem solving activities.
2. The mathematics performance of the freshmen pre-service teachers fell within the very satisfactory level, implying that students developed fundamental knowledge and skills in mathematics subject.
3. The correlation analysis showed that all four mathematical curiosity dimensions —epistemic curiosity, perceptual curiosity, exploration, and absorption—have a positive relationship with freshmen pre-service teachers' mathematics performance. The means that intrinsic interest and fascination of freshmen pre-service teachers may have some influence on their performance in mathematics.
4. The regression analysis revealed that among the domains of mathematical curiosity, only exploration significantly predicts the mathematics performance of the freshmen pre-service teachers.

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Recommendation

1. The freshmen pre-service teachers show a high level of mathematical curiosity. It is recommended to keep offering engaging activities (cooperative problem-solving, themed activities, puzzles, and riddles) to help them overcome challenges and boost their math skills.
2. Some freshmen pre-service teachers didn't do very well in math. To help them understand better, it's recommended to have programs with fun, and hands-on activities in mathematics. The freshmen pre-service teachers should try to find what makes them curious about math, like learning new things, seeing patterns, exploring, and really getting into it.
3. A significant correlation exists between the freshmen pre-service teacher's mathematical curiosity and their mathematics performance. It's a recommend to add activities that boost their curiosity, like group problem-solving sessions, unfamiliar problems, and abstract concepts. Teachers can also encourage curiosity by praising their achievements, giving helpful feedback, and highlighting how important it is to keep trying and putting in effort to learn math.
4. Only exploration, out of the four dimensions of mathematical curiosity examined, was a strong predictor of math performance. It's recommended to focus on teaching methods that let students learn by asking questions, figuring things out themselves, and working on real-world projects in mathematics.
5. Future research into the relationship between mathematical curiosity and mathematics performance among high school students, including non-cognitive factors, is recommended.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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